

H2020 DAEMON Project
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Deliverable 6.3

Report on Communication, dissemination and exploitation results and updated CoDEP for Y3

Abstract

This deliverable summarizes the results attained by the project in year 2 of the H2020 DAEMON project in terms of dissemination and communication, standardization and open-source activities, and exploitation and innovation. Moreover, it presents the communication, dissemination, and exploitation plan for year 3 (CoDEPv3). Here we provide the list of the achieved and planned activities as well as the targeted metrics. We also look at how we have changed our approach to how we engage with some of the targeted open-source projects in Y2 and beyond.

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List of Acronyms

3GPP	– Third Generation Partnership Project
5GPPP	– 5G Public Private Partnership
6G-IA	– 6G Smart Networks and Services Industry Association
AAAI	– Association for the Advancement of AI
AI	– Artificial Intelligence
AR	– Augmented Reality
B5G	– Beyond 5G
CoDEP	– Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan
CVD	– Coordinated Vulnerability Disclosure
DOC	– Digital Operations Center
DOI	– Digital Object Identifier System
DU	– Distributed Unit
eNB	– evolved Node B
ENI	– Experimental Networked Intelligence
ETSI	– European Telecommunications Standards Institute
FPGA	– Field Programmable Gate Array
gNB	– Next Generation NodeB
GSMA	– Groupe Speciale Mobile Association
IEEE	– Institute of Electronics and Electrical Engineering
IETF	– Internet Engineering Task Force
IoT	– Internet of Things
IPR	– Intellectual Property Rights
IRTF	– Internet Research Task Force
ISG	– Industry Standards Group
ITU-T	– International Telecommunications Union – Telecommunications standardization sector
KPI	– Key Performance Indicator
L4S	– Low Latency, Low Loss, Scalable Throughput
MANO	– Management and orchestration
MEC	– Multi-access Edge Computing
ML	– Machine Learning
NFV	– Network Function Virtualization
NI	– Network Intelligence
NIS	– Network Information System
OEM	– Original Equipment Manufacturer
OPNFV	– Open Platform for NFV
ORAN	– Open Radio Access Network
O-RAN	– ORAN Alliance
PoC	– Proof of Concept
R&D	– Research and Development
RAN	– Radio Access Network
RF	– Radio Frequency
RFC	– Request for Comments
RIS	– Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface
S1	– Interface that connects the RAN to the core
S1AP	– S1 Application Protocol
SDO	– Standard Development Organization
SDN	– Software Defined Networking
SM	– Standardization manager
SME	– Small and medium-sized enterprise
SCTP	– Stream Control Transmission Protocol
TSG	– Technical Specification Groups
UE	– User Equipment

V2X – Vehicle to Everything

VNF – Virtual Network Function

VR – Virtual Reality

vRAN – virtualized Radio Access Network

WG – Working Group

WP – Work Package

XR – Extended Reality

ZSM – Zero touch network and Service Management

Executive summary

The main contributions of this document are:

- Presentation of the main achievements during the second year of the project.
- Presentation of the communication, dissemination, and exploitation plan for the third year of the project (CoDEPv3).

DAEMON's CoDEP includes communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities. **Communication** includes all the activities related to the promotion of the project and its results beyond the project's own community. This includes explaining its research in layman's terms to the media and the public. **Dissemination** includes activities related to raising awareness of its results in a technical community working in the same research field. In general, this will be done through publications, participation, and the organization of technical events. Finally, **exploitation** (in accordance with the European IPR Helpdesk) covers activities aiming at using the results in further research activities other than those covered by the project, such as developing, creating and marketing products or processes, creating and providing a service, or standardization activities.

The project is currently entering its third year, with the last year (Y2) being the second year of the project. Meaning the project was in the **Presentation of Results** phase. This is inline with the communication, dissemination and exploitation plan of the project. During Y2, dissemination and exploitation activities increased their intensity, since the architecture and NI design efforts have produced some initial research outcomes. Initial demonstrations of specific architecture concepts and NI solutions were also provided during this phase. However, in the **Demos and PoCs** phase, demonstration activities involving multiple blocks of the architecture working in an integrated way are expected. This will be the focus of Y3. Finally, the **Long-lasting Impact** phase refers to other research or exploitation actions taken once the project is finished. This includes shaping the topics and framework of future research projects, exploiting DAEMON NI concepts in a market-oriented way by incorporating them into products and services, and leaving a footprint in standards through project contributions. The plan defines the various undertaken activities and defines related target metrics.

Below, we highlight the main outcomes of Year 2:

- Communication Activities:
 - Two press articles covering DAEMON have been released.
 - Seven videos have been published.
 - Six webinars and three workshops were organized.
 - Three DAEMON public deliverables were submitted.
 - DAEMON web page, social media profiles (i.e., Twitter, Facebook, Facebook Page, Instagram, LinkedIn, and Youtube), and data repositories (i.e., Zenodo and OpenAIRE) have been actively managed.
- Disseminations Activities:
 - 24 scientific conference and workshop publications (including many top-ranked venues like ACM SIGCOMM, ACM MobiCom, ACM CoNEXT, IEEE INFOCOM or AAAI).
 - Five JCR-indexed publications in scientific journals.
 - Participation in various working groups to join efforts with other 5G PPP projects.
- Exploitation Activities:
 - 28 accepted contributions to SDOs.
 - Five contributions to open-source projects.
 - Five DAEMON products accepted in the Innovation Radar.

1 Introduction

DAEMON's Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan (CoDEP) covers the following three types of activities:

- **Communication Activities:** These activities encompass all actions concerning the promotion of the project and its results beyond the project's own community. In this way, the target of this activity is the general public, i.e., non-specialists, and the message is encoded in a way that this audience understands.
- **Dissemination activities:** These activities aim to raise awareness of DAEMON's results in a technical community, i.e., working in the same field of research. These activities are usually performed through peer-reviewed publications in scientific conferences and journals, and through participation and organization of technical events (e.g., workshops, tutorials, etc.).
- **Exploitation activities:** These activities cover initiatives that foster further research activities, i.e., other than those covered by DAEMON. These include:
 - Activities to develop, create, and market products or processes
 - Activities to create and provide a service
 - Standardization activities.

Figure 1: DAEMON Dissemination & Exploitation Plan for Y1 to end of the project.

Figure 1 shows the various phases of the dissemination, communication, and exploitation activities of the project from Y1 to Y3 and beyond the end of the project. During Y2, the project was in the "Presentation of Results" phase. This document will outline the activities carried out during this time while also laying forth the plan for Y3 and the "Demos and PoCs" phase of the project.

During year 1, the project was in the "Raise Awareness" phase (M0 to M11). The results of this are clearly laid out in D6.2 [1].

During year 2, the "Presentation of results" phase, the project increased its focus on dissemination and exploitation activities. This phase resulted in a substantial number of research papers being published outlining our initial research outcomes. Further analytical results gathered via simulations were also generated during this stage and disseminated at top-tier scientific conferences and workshops. Preliminary demonstrations were also carried out at events such as Mobile World Congress and EuCNC.

Efforts towards contributing to open-source projects and SDOs also increased during this phase of the project. Multiple contributions were made to Zenoh, Zenoh-flow, and srsRAN, bringing us in line with our planned open-source contributions for the first two years of the project. Our increased effort to contribute to SDOs led to over twenty-five contributions to various bodies, including ETSI-RIS, 3GPP, ORAN, and others.

Exploitation activities during this time led to the successful acceptance of five innovations from the project being accepted to the EU Innovation Radar Platform. Other exploitation activities included the generation of multiple patents, datasets, and academic activities during Y2.

Over the course of Y2, we focused strongly on the following activities:

- Dissemination:
 - Publication of research results in scientific conferences, workshops and journals.
 - Enrolment of PhD and Master students on the topics of the project.
 - Participation in public exhibitions and demonstrations.
 - Organization of special events (e.g., technical workshops).
 - Collaboration with other projects.
- Exploitation:
 - Identification of products and services, integrating NI spawning from DAEMON work.
 - Issuing patents and licensing.
 - Contribution to relevant open-source software projects.
 - Contribution to standardization bodies.

During the “Demos and PoCs” phase, DAEMON will re-focus its efforts on developing demonstration and proof-of-concept (PoC) prototypes of designed NI-aided systems. These activities will help validate the NI mechanisms derived in other work packages and, in the context of WP6, will help disseminate and communicate the project results to the scientific community and the general public.

The final stage of the CoDEP is named “Long-lasting impact”, which will begin towards the end of the project implementation and will last several months after DAEMON has finished. During this stage, partners of DAEMON will keep disseminating the results of the project and exploiting network intelligence designed and developed during DAEMON by impacting the product or service portfolio of the vendors in the consortium or through enforcing IPR and licenses.

This CoDEP is periodically updated (this deliverable presents the plan for Y3) throughout the project's lifetime. This allows us to accommodate new activities, such as new collaboration or dissemination opportunities, should they appear. In the rest of this document, we present the major achievements during the second year of the project, as well as the plan of communication, dissemination and exploitation activities for the third year of the project.

This document presents the main achievement of Y2 and the revised plan for Y3. The main achievements from Y2 are summarized as follows:

- Communication Activities:
 - Two press articles delivered.
 - Four oral communications provided.
 - Seven videos published.
 - Eight photos of a DAEMON event published.
 - Eight webinars organized.
 - Two workshops organized.
 - Five DAEMON public deliverables submitted.
 - 405 social network posts published.
 - 5519 DAEMON website new visits.
 - Each DAEMON asset has an average of 229 views which 190 are downloads.
- Disseminations Activities:
 - 24 scientific conference and workshop publications (including many top-ranked venues like ACM SIGCOMM, ACM MobiCom, ACM CoNEXT, IEEE INFOCOM or AAAI).
 - Five JCR-indexed publications in scientific journals.
 - Participation in various working groups to join efforts with other 5G PPP projects.
- Exploitation Activities:
 - Five DAEMON products accepted in the Innovation Radar.
 - Five open-source contributions.

2 Achievements in Year 2

2.1 Communication Activities

2.1.1 News and Press Releases

Two press articles covering DAEMON have been released. Specifically:

1. (17/11/2022) Laying the groundwork for Beyond 5G success by Marco Fiore and A.García-Saavedra (IMDEA, NEC): https://cordis.europa.eu/article/id/442590-laying-the-groundwork-for-beyond-5g-success?WT.mc_id=exp
2. (03/11/2022) Advancing the integration of Artificial Intelligence to improve the efficiency and sustainability of mobile network architectures by Marco Fiore (IMDEA): <https://networks.imdea.org/advancing-the-integration-of-artificial-intelligence-to-improve-the-efficiency-and-sustainability-of-mobile-network-architectures/>

Four oral communications related to DAEMON have been released. Specifically:

1. (08/12/2022) The 6G Architecture Landscape European perspective by M.Gramaglia (UC3M) at 6G Arch Workshop at Globecom: <https://globecom2022.ieee-globecom.org/program/technical-workshops/ws18-2nd-workshop-architectural-evolution-toward-6g-0>
2. (19/09/2022) WiOpt'22 by Andra Lutu (Telefónica I+D+I): <https://www.wi-opt.org/program.html>
3. (29/08/2022) DAEMON Presentation at XAISS eXplainable AI Summer School 2022 by Livia Elena Chatzieleftheriou (IMDEA): <https://xaiss.eu/>
4. (22/03/2022) Applied Machine Learning Days – AI & Telco by Telefónica I+D: <https://appliedmldays.org/highlights/565>

Seven videos have been published:

1. (09/05/2022) DAEMON EuCNC'22 overview: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7215964>
2. (09/05/2022) DAEMON EuCNC'22 activity: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7215974>
3. (22/06/2022) DAEMON PROMO: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7215978>
4. (16/06/2022) Defining Categorical Reasoning of Numerical Feature Models with Feature-Wise and Variant-Wise Quality Attributes by UMA: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7552222>
5. (16/09/2022) Quality-aware Analysis and Optimisation of Virtual Network Functions by UMA: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7551778>
6. (16/09/2022) NEMO: A Tool to Support Feature Models with Numerical Features and Arithmetic Constraints by UMA: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6672342>
7. (16/09/2022) Composición Categórica de Análisis Automáticos para Líneas de Productos Extendidas by UMA

We contributed to eight webinars:

1. (19/01/2022) DAEMON: Machine learning-based resource orchestration in beyond-5G networks by D. De Vleeschauwer at ICT-52 Workshop on 6G: <https://hexa-x.eu/ict-52-workshop-on-6g-2023/>
2. (19/01/2022) DAEMON: A network intelligence plane for 6G networks by M. Gramaglia at ICT-52 Workshop on 6G: <https://hexa-x.eu/ict-52-workshop-on-6g-2023/>
3. (30/09/2022) NGN Webinar 2022 by Telefónica I+D: <https://coseners.net/ngn-webinar-series/>
4. (28/09/2022) Workshop on 6G KPIs and how to measure them by IMDEA Networks Institute: <https://5g-ppp.eu/event/workshop-on-6g-kpis-and-how-to-measure-them/>
5. (02/04/2022) DAEMON: Learning to Predict for Automated Network Management by IMDEA Networks Institute and UC3M: <https://hexa-x.eu/ict-52-workshop-on-6g/>
6. (02/03/2022) DAEMON Webinar: Reliable RAN Virtualization in Shared Platforms by NEC/UC3M/IMDEA: <https://hexa-x.eu/ict-52-workshop-on-6g/>
7. (02/03/2022) DAEMON Webinar: Energy-aware Orchestration of Virtualized RANs: Experiments and Algorithms by TU Delft: <https://hexa-x.eu/ict-52-workshop-on-6g/>
8. (19/01/2022) DAEMON Webinar: RAN Virtualization by NEC.

Three workshops were organized:

1. NativeNI 2022 - The 1st International Workshop on Native Network Intelligence by IMDEA: <https://nativeni.github.io/>
2. 2nd International Workshop on Autonomous Network Management in 5G and Beyond Systems (ANSM 2023) by IMEC and NBL: <https://h2020daemon.eu/workshop-ansm-2023/>

3. 6G Arch at Globecom 2022 by UC3M: <https://5g-ppp.eu/6garch-workshop-globecol-2022-call-for-papers/>

We have also made available DAEMON five public deliverables:

1. (07/08/2022) Deliverable 2.2 "Initial DAEMON Network Intelligence framework and toolsets": <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6970839>
2. (06/07/2022) Deliverable 5.1 "Preliminary Evaluation Results and Plan for Proof-of-Concept Demonstrations": <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6801832>
3. (28/01/2022) Deliverable 6.2 "Report on Communication, dissemination and exploitation results and updated CoDEP for Y2": <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5930346>
4. D3.2 "Refined design of real-time control and VNF intelligence mechanisms" on November 30th, 2022: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7525876>
5. D4.2 "Refined design of intelligent orchestration and management mechanisms" on November 30th, 2022: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7544155>

2.1.2 Web, Social Media and Project Communication Material

We keep managing and updating DAEMON's official server and website, which is reachable through the following URL: <https://h2020daemon.eu/>. The deliverables page is shown in Figure 2. DAEMON Deliverable page on project website

CONTACT AND MEDIA

Figure 2. DAEMON Deliverable page on project website.

We are collecting visibility metrics based on many analytic services. Based on Advanced Page Visit Counter, we present their analytics in Figure 3. We have a total of 34400 unique visits while 20400 accounts for 2022 from which 1700 are just from December, leaving 456 from the last week of the year. Additionally, the landing page (i.e., Home) has been the most visited, with approximately 20 unique loads a day.

Figure 3. Total DAEMON website visits.

Google Analytics provides the results of Figure 4. It can be observed that from the 20400 loads, 5519 were unique website visits, from which 2521 of them were of totally different IPs. Compared to Year 1, we almost doubled the numbers. Again, Home, followed by the ANMS'22 workshop page, and the Publications page had the most traffic.

Page title and screen class	↓ Views	Users	Views per user
	5,519 100% of total	2,521 100% of total	2.19 Avg 0%
1 Home - DAEMON: Network intelligence aDAptive sElf-Learning MOBILE Networks	2,168	1,295	1.67
2 ANMS'22 - DAEMON: Network intelligence aDAptive sElf-Learning MOBILE Networks	1,086	932	1.17
3 Publications - DAEMON: Network intelligence aDAptive sElf-Learning MOBILE Networks	345	176	1.96
4 About - DAEMON: Network intelligence aDAptive sElf-Learning MOBILE Networks	291	165	1.76
5 Overview - DAEMON: Network intelligence aDAptive sElf-Learning MOBILE Networks	261	163	1.60
6 Deliverables - DAEMON: Network intelligence aDAptive sElf-Learning MOBILE Networks	250	160	1.56
7 Consortium - DAEMON: Network intelligence aDAptive sElf-Learning MOBILE Networks	215	162	1.33
8 Media - DAEMON: Network intelligence aDAptive sElf-Learning MOBILE Networks	133	94	1.41
9 Objectives - DAEMON: Network intelligence aDAptive sElf-Learning MOBILE Networks	124	84	1.48
10 Documentation - DAEMON: Network intelligence aDAptive sElf-Learning MOBILE Networks	98	64	1.53
11 ANSM'22 - DAEMON: Network intelligence aDAptive sElf-Learning MOBILE Networks	95	87	1.09
12 Methodology - DAEMON: Network intelligence aDAptive sElf-Learning MOBILE Networks	94	65	1.45
13 Contact Us - DAEMON: Network intelligence aDAptive sElf-Learning MOBILE Networks	86	65	1.32
14 ANMS'23 - DAEMON: Network intelligence aDAptive sElf-Learning MOBILE Networks	64	28	2.29
15 Data Sets - DAEMON: Network intelligence aDAptive sElf-Learning MOBILE Networks	64	43	1.49
16 News and Events - DAEMON: Network intelligence aDAptive sElf-Learning MOBILE Networks	59	40	1.48

Figure 4. Google Analytics Report of most visited pages.

Further, based on the results of Figure 5, Our followers tend to access through Desktop or Laptop devices, occasionally through mobile devices, and anecdotally through tablets.

Figure 5. Google Analytics Report of devices used to access DAEMON site.

Then, based on the results of Figure 6, visitors mostly use Chrome web explorer, far followed by Safari, Firefox, and UC Browser. Anecdotally, they use Internet Explorer and Samsung OEM explorer.

Figure 6. Google Analytics Report of web-browsers used to access DAEMON site.

The last statistics from Google Analytics are the demographics of Figure 7, where it is important to highlight the two “superpower” countries besides the ones from the European Union ones: The United States of America and The United Kingdom. Spanish audience was also expected as some of our communications are in Spanish venues.

Figure 7. Google Analytics Report of DAEMON site demographics.

We keep active the different DAEMON social network profiles, which are:

1. Twitter: <https://twitter.com/h2020daemon>
2. Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/h2020daemon>
3. Facebook Page: <https://www.facebook.com/h2020daemoneu/>
4. Instagram: <https://www.instagram.com/h2020daemon/>
5. LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/daemon-daemon-717591202/>
6. Youtube: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCbccd2DulaSMX_69uaLZy7A

All these accounts are shared on our webpage, and Twitter and Facebook feeds are displayed in real-time throughout it. A total of 405 meaningful posts have been shared (81 per social network, besides one on YouTube). In Twitter, we have reached the best numbers; a total of 16500 impressions, which is a ~40% increase compared to Year 1. In Figure 8, we can see its analytics for the last three months, where our mention at the AI Summer School was the most popular, followed by the Plenary Meetings follow-up.

Figure 8. Twitter Analytics Report of tweets impressions and engagement of the last three months.

On average, we doubled the engagement ratio. Figure 9 shows the Twitter profile of DAEMON, which shows that 76 accounts are subscribed to our news.

Figure 9. Official Profile of DAEMON on Twitter.

The rest of the social networks show similar analytics. In addition, the updated DAEMON Project Tri-Fold Kick-off Brochure was submitted and distributed as Open Access on 24th February 2022. It also contains analytics for the number of digital views, downloads, and QR scans. While Figure 10 shows its A-side, it is completely accessible, and ready to cite, using the following DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6264798>

Figure 10. The H2020 European Project DAEMON Tri-Fold Kick-off Brochure of 2022.

In terms of communication KPIs in numbers:

- We committed to publishing two press releases per year, which we accomplished.
- We committed to organizing a total of two academic workshops/conferences and currently accomplished a rate of three per DAEMON's year.
- We committed to organizing a total of two industrial workshops/conferences and attending 10 events. We are currently organizing two for 2023 and attended seven industrial events.
- We committed to advertising our website to reach over 75% of the visits from outside of the consortium, and it is currently above that number considering the ones from USA, UK, China, etc.
- Among 11 uploaded videos, we professionally recorded one Promotional video for the DAEMON YouTube channel and Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7215978>), as well as several PowerPoint slides from conference presentations in the DAEMON Zenodo community. Likewise, the brochure was updated and published. They are also automatically populated to the DAEMON OpenAIRE profile.

2.2 Dissemination Activities

In this section, we summarize the dissemination activities of the project just for the second year. DAEMON has carried out multiple dissemination activities, even if the project is still not finished, and this includes presentations in multiple conferences, seminars and forums.

2.2.1 Publications and Technical Dissemination

The following tables present DAEMON peer-reviewed articles in scientific journals and studies, demos, and posters in scientific conferences. In the first column of each table, we also specify the corresponding tasks that are related to these publications. The rows in each table are ordered by publication date from the oldest to the newest.

Table 1 presents 27 publications in scientific conferences (**C**) and workshops (**W**) at top-tier venues like IEEE INFOCOM, ACM SIGCOMM, SPLC and MobiCom. Table 2 presents six publications in top-tier scientific journals, like IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing, IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications, and IEEE/ACM Transactions on Networking. We also remark that many of such top-quality contributions stem from multiparty collaborative work within the DAEMON consortium. Among them, we highlight the work "Forecasting for Network Management with Joint Statistical Modelling and Machine Learning" between IMDEA and UC3M, as well as the Demonstration of Nuberu by UC3M, and I2CAT.

Besides these specific collaboration, project wide contributions have been disseminated also through scientific papers like the ones published at CCNC 2022 and EuCNC 2022.

Table 1. Publications in scientific conferences (type C) and workshops (type W).

Date & Tasks	Type	Title	Event	Authors	Open Access DOI
05/01 T2.3	C	LossLeaP: Learning to Predict for Intent-Based Networking	IEEE INFOCOM 2022	A. Collet, A. Banchs, M. Fiore	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6351613
11/01 T2.1 T2.2	W	Requirements and Specifications for the Orchestration of Network Intelligence in 6G	CCNC 2022 WKSHPs: 6G: What to expect from 6G: visions, use cases and technologies	Miguel Camelo, Luca Cominardi, Marco Gramaglia, Marco Fiore, Andres Garcia-Saavedra, Lidia Fuentes, Danny De Vleeschauwer, Paola Soto-Arenas, Nina Slamnik-Krijestorac, Joaquín Ballesteros, Chia-Yu Chang, Gabriele Baldoni, Johann M. Marquez-Barja, Peter Hellinckx, and Steven Latré	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5767861
02/02 T4.4	C	Analyse or Transmit: Utilising Correlation at the Edge with Deep Reinforcement Learning	IEEE Global Communications Conference (GLOBECOM)	Jernej Hribar, Ryoichi Shinkuma, George Iosifidis, and Ivana Dusparic	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7038317
05/02 T5.2	C	Demonstrating Nuberu: A Reliable DU Design Suitable for Virtualization Platforms	ACM MobiCom 2021	Gines Garcia-Aviles, Andres Garcia-Saavedra, Marco Gramaglia, Xavier Costa-Perez, Pablo Serrano, Albert Banchs	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6241555
10/06 T2.4	C	SLAs Decomposition for Network Slicing: A Deep Neural Network Approach	International Conference on Computing Systems	Cyril Shih-Huan Hsu, Danny De Vleeschauwer, Chrysa Papagianni	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6685244
16/06 T3.2	C	NEMO: A Tool to Transform Feature Models with Numerical Features and	International Conference on Software and Systems Reuse (ICSR) 2022	Daniel-Jesus Munoz, Jeho Oh, Monica Pinto, Lidia Fuentes, Don Batory	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6657675

		Arithmetic Constraints			
16/06 T2.1 T3.2	C	Composición Categórica de Análisis Automáticos para Líneas de Productos Extendidas	Jornadas de Ingeniería del Software y Bases de Datos (JISBD) 2022	Daniel-Jesus Munoz, Monica Pinto, Lidia Fuentes	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6658079
27/06 T4.2	C	Global mobile network aggregators: taxonomy, roaming performance and optimization	ACM MobiSys 2022	Sergi Alcalá-Marín, Aravindh Raman, Weili Wu, Andra Lutu, Marcelo Bagnulo, Ozgu Alay, Fabian E. Bustamante	https://doi.org/10.1145/3498361.3538942
28/06 T2.1 T3.2	C	Defining Categorical Reasoning of Numerical Feature Models with Feature-Wise and Variant-Wise Quality Attributes	26th ACM International Systems and Software Product Lines Conference (SPLC'22)	Daniel-Jesus Munoz, Monica Pinto, Dilian Gurov, Lidia Fuentes	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6826201
28/06 T2.1 T3.2	C	Quality-aware Analysis and Optimisation of Virtual Network Functions	26th ACM International Systems and Software Product Lines Conference (SPLC'22)	Daniel-Jesus Munoz, Monica Pinto, Lidia Fuentes	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6772503
08/07 T2.1 T2.2 T2.3 T2.4	C	Network Intelligence for Virtualized RAN Orchestration: The DAEMON Approach	EuCNC 2022	Marco Gramaglia ; Miguel Camelo ; Lidia Fuentes and Joaquín Ballesteros ; Luca Cominardi and Gabriele Baldoni ; Andres Garcia-Saavedra ; Marco Fiore	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6820938
22/07 T5.2	C	Online Caching with Optimistic Learning	2022 IFIP Networking Conference (IFIP Networking)	Naram Mhaisen; George Iosifidis; Douglas Leith	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7038255
07/08 T4.3 T4.4	W	Framework for Trustworthy AI/ML in B5G/6G	2nd Workshop on Accountability, Liability and Trust for 5G and Beyond, 1st International Conf. on 6G Networking (6GNet 2022)	Sokratis Barmponakis, Panagiotis Demestichas	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6656606
23/08 T3.2	C	Forecasting for Network Management with Joint Statistical Modelling and Machine Learning	23rd IEEE International Symposium on A World of Wireless, Mobile and Multimedia Networks (WoWMoM), 2022	Lo Schiavo, Leonardo; Fiore, Marco; Gramaglia, Marco; Banchs, Albert; Costa-Perez, Xavier	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7016890
17/10 T3.4 T5.2	W	Designing, Building, and Characterizing RF-Switch-based	ACM WINTeCH 2022	M. Rossanese, P. Mursia, A. Garcia-Saavedra, V. Sciancalepore, A.	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7357953

		Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces		Asadi, X. Costa-Perez	
15/11 T2.1 T2.2	C	Realizing Flat Multi-Zone Multi-Controller Software-Defined Networks using Zenoh	8th IEEE Conference on Network Functions Virtualization and Software-Defined Networking, 2022.	Federico Giarre, Luca Cominardi (ZSCALE), Paolo Casari	https://hdl.handle.net/11572/355882
29/11 T4.1 T4.4	C	Energy-aware placement of network functions in edge-based infrastructures with Open Source MANO and Kubernetes	FMCIoT 2022	Angel Cañete, Alberto Rodriguez, Mercedes Amor and Lidia Fuentes	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5075287
06/12 T4.1 T4.4	C	A proactive energy-aware auto-scaling solution for edge-based infrastructures	CloudAM 2022	Angel Cañete, Karim Djemame, Mercedes Amor, Lidia Fuentes and Abdullah Aljulayfi	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7249831
09/12 T3.4 T5.2	W	Henna: Hierarchical Machine Learning Inference in Programmable Switches	The 1st International Workshop on Native Network Intelligence 2022	A.T.-J. Akem, B. Bütün, M. Gucciardo, M. Fiore	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7543596
20/05 /2023 T3.4 T5.2	C	Flowrest: Practical Flow-Level Inference in Programmable Switches with Random Forests	IEEE INFOCOM 2023	A.T.-J. Akem, M. Gucciardo, M. Fiore	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7550150
20/05 /2023 T2.4 T4.2 T5.3	C	AutoManager: a Meta-Learning Model for Network Management from Intertwined Forecasts	IEEE INFOCOM 2023	A. Collet, A. Bazco Noguerras, A. Banchs, M. Fiore	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7550176
20/05 /2023 T2.4 T4.2 T5.3	C	Spotting Deep Neural Network Vulnerabilities in Mobile Traffic Forecasting with an Explainable AI Lens	IEEE INFOCOM 2023	S. Moghadas, C. Fiandrino, A. Collet, G. Attanasio, M. Fiore, J. Widmer	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7550186
20/05 /2023 T3.1 T5.2	C	Spotlight on 5G: Performance, Device Evolution and Challenges from a Mobile Operator Perspective	IEEE INFOCOM 2023	P. Parastar, A. Lutu, O. Alay, G. Caso, D. Perino	<i>It has been accepted, but as the authors are filing a patent based on this work, we cannot provide an Open DOI yet</i>
12/01 /2023 T2.1 T2.2 T2.3 T2.4	W	DAEMON: A Network Intelligence Plane for 6G Networks	2022 IEEE Globecom Workshops (GC Workshops)	Camelo, Miguel; Gramaglia, Marco; Soto, Paola; Fuentes, Lidia; Ballesteros, Joaquín; Bazco-Noguerras, Antonio; Garcia-Aviles, Gines; Latré, Steven; Garcia-	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.755198

				Saavedra, Andres; Fiore, Marco;	
01/12/2022 T4.2	C	Energy-aware Scheduling of Virtualized Base Stations in O-RAN with Online Learning	IEEE Global Communications Conference (GLOBECOM)	Michail Kalntis, George Iosifidis	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7569184
22/12/2022 T5.2	C	Optimistic No-Regret Algorithms for Discrete Caching	ACM SIGMETRICS 2023	Naram Mhaisen; Abhishek Sinha; Georgios Paschos; George Iosifidis (TU Delft)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7565019
22/12/2021 T4.1 T4.4 T5.2	C	Enabling Long-term Fairness in Dynamic Resource Allocation	ACM SIGMETRICS 2023	Tareq Si Salem; Georgios Iosifidis; Giovanni Neglia (TU Delft)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7564978

Four presentation slides were also uploaded to Zenodo to complement these publications. Such presentations concretely are:

1. (16/06/2022) "NEMO: A Tool to Support Feature Models with Numerical Features and Arithmetic Constraints" by UMA at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6672326>
2. (16/09/2022) "Defining Categorical Reasoning of Numerical Feature Models with Feature-Wise and Variant-Wise Quality Attributes" by UMA at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7552224>
3. (16/09/2022) "Quality-aware Analysis and Optimisation of Virtual Network Functions" by UMA at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7551778>
4. (09/09/2022) "Composición Categórica de Análisis Automáticos para Líneas de Productos Extendidas" by UMA at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7554720>

Table 2. Publications in scientific journals.

Date & Tasks	Title	Journal	Authors	Open Access DOI
09/01 T2.3	Toward Native Explainable and Robust AI in 6G Networks: Current State, Challenges and Road Ahead	Elsevier Computer Communications	C. Fiandrino, G. Attanasio, M. Fiore, J. Widmer	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6351613
01/04 T2.3	Privacy-Preserving AI for Future Networks	Communications of the ACM	Diego Perino, Kleomenis Katevas, Andra Lutu, Eduard Marin, Nicolas Kourtellis	https://dl.acm.org/doi/pdf/10.1145/3512343
20/07 T3.2	RadiOrchestra: Proactive Management of Millimeter-wave Self-backhauled Small Cells via Joint Optimization of Beamforming, User Association, Rate Selection, and Admission Control	IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications	Luis F. Abanto-Leon, Arash Asadi, Andres Garcia-Saavedra, Gek Hong (Allyson) Sim, Matthias Hollick	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6974569
31/08 T3.2	Migration-Aware Network Services with Edge Computing	IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management	Atri Mukhopadhyay, George Iosifidis, and Marco Ruffini	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7038273
05/09 T5.1 T5.2 T5.3	Design and Validation of an Open Source Cloud Native Mobile Network	IEEE Communications Magazine	Nikolaos Apostolakis, Marco Gramaglia, Pablo Serrano	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7053585

01/05 /2022 T4.1 T4.4 T5.2	Selective Edge Computing for Mobile Analytics	IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management	Apostolos Galanopoulos; George Iosifidis; Theodoros Salonidis; Douglas J. Leith (TU Delft)	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7565476
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Additionally, we edited one journal special issue and co-edited another journal regular issue, which respectively are:

Table 3. Edited Issues.

Date	Special Issue	Publisher	Authorship	URL
01/03	Network management for beyond 5G systems	Journal of Network and Systems Management	IMEC, UC3M and NEC	https://research.com/special-issue/network-management-for-beyond-5g-systems-2
24/09	Network Application Software for Vertical IoT Industry	IEEE IoT Magazine	NBL	https://www.comsoc.org/publications/magazines/ieee-internet-things-magazine/cfp/network-application-software-vertical-iot

Further, the scientific conference poster entitled "Designing, Building, and Characterizing RF-Switch-based Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces" by NEC was published on **17/10/2022** at ACM MobiCom 2022: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7551269>.

Finally, three whitepapers were published:

Table 4. Whitepapers publications.

Date & Tasks	Title	Publisher	Author	Open Access DOI
10/06 T2.2 T2.4	6G Technology Overview - One6G White Paper	One6G	Carlos Guimaraes, Luca Cominardi et al.	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6630706
01/06 T5.1 T5.2 T5.3	Beyond 5G/6G KPIs and Target Values	5GPPP Test, Measurement and KPIs Validation WG White Paper	Vangelis Kosmatos, Andres Garcia Saavedra	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6577506
08/12 T2.1 T2.2 T2.3 T2.4	The 6G Architecture Landscape - European perspective	5GPPP Architecture Work Group	Marco Gramaglia	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7313232

In terms of dissemination KPIs in numbers:

- We committed to providing a total of 80 high-tier publications, and since the beginning of the project we have accumulated 16 journals, three magazines, 48 conferences, seven workshops, five whitepapers, three demonstration papers, one scientific poster and six slides, which makes **a total of 83 publications to date** plus the slides.
- We committed to publishing a total of four demonstrations, and we currently succeeded with **three operational demonstrators to date**.
- We committed to editing two special issues, and we currently **published one and co-edited two regular issues**.

Finally, in Figure 11 we can see an example of the analytics for DAEMON publications. In general, each asset has at least 299 views and 190 downloads. Nevertheless, there are natural variations depending on how old the contribution is.

Figure 11. Example of the Zenodo analytics for each published asset in the DAEMON community.

2.2.2 Synergies with Other Projects

The DAEMON project carried out several collaborative activities with other projects funded under 5G PPP calls towards a coordinated action inside the 5G-PPP during its second year. Such activities are summarized in Table 5 below and include joint research and publication of scientific results, participation in 5G PPP boards and Working Groups (WG), and contributions to white papers, webinars, brochures, and special sessions.

Table 5. Activities of DAEMON in the framework of 5G PPP and/or jointly with other projects.

Item	Explanation
Joint Paper	Joint scientific publication with the H2020 project "Hexa-X - A flagship for 5G/6G vision and intelligent fabric of technology enablers connecting human, physical, and digital worlds (101015956)" titled "Design and Validation of an Open Source Cloud Native Mobile Network" at IEEE Communications Magazine by Apostolakis, Nikolaos; Gramaglia, Marco; and Serrano, Pablo.
Joint Paper	Joint scientific demo paper with the H2020 project "Hexa-X - A flagship for 5G/6G vision and intelligent fabric of technology enablers connecting human, physical, and digital worlds (101015956)" titled "Demo: Nuberu - A Reliable DU Design Suitable for Virtualization Platforms" at IEEE Communications Magazine by Apostolakis, Nikolaos; Gramaglia, Marco; and Serrano, Pablo.
5G PPP board	Participation in Steering Board (M. Fiore – IMDEA)
5G PPP board	Participation in Technical Board (A. Garcia-Saavedra – NEC)
5G PPP WG	Participation in 5G Architecture WG (Xi Li – NEC, M. Gramaglia – UC3M, M. Camelo – IMEC)
5G PPP WG	Participation in Vision and Societal Challenges WG (M. Fiore – IMDEA)
5G PPP WG	Participation in Software Networks WG (C.-Y. Chang – NOKIA, J. Marquez-Barja – IMEC)
5G PPP WG	Participation in 5G Automotive WG (J. Marquez-Barja – IMEC)
5G PPP WG	Participation in Test, Measurement and KPIs Validation WG (A. Garcia-Saavedra – NEC, V. Kosmatos – WINGS)
5G PPP WG	Participation in Pre-Standardization WG (M. Gucciardo – IMDEA)
5G PPP WG	Participation in Open Smart Networks and Services WG (A. Garcia-Saavedra)
5G PPP oral communication	"The 6G Architecture Landscape" at 6G Arch Workshop at Globecom 2022 by M.Gramaglia (UC3M)
5G PPP workshop organization	"6G Arch" at Globecom 2022 by M.Gramaglia (UC3M)" by V. Kosmatos, M. Fiore (IMDEA)
	"Workshop on 6G KPIs and how to measure them"

5G PPP webinar	"Workshop on 6G KPIs and how to measure them" by V. Kosmatos, M. Fiore (IMDEA)
5G PPP webinar	"DAEMON: A network intelligence plane for 6G networks" at 5G PPP ICT-52 Workshop on 6G by M.Gramaglia (UC3M)
5G PPP webinar	"DAEMON: Machine learning-based resource orchestration in beyond-5G networks" at 5G PPP ICT-52 Workshop on 6G by D. De Vleeschauwer (Nokia)
5G PPP webinar	"DAEMON: RAN Virtualization" at 5GPPP TB by A. Garcia Saavedra (NEC)
5G PPP webinar	"DAEMON: Energy-aware Orchestration of Virtualized RANs: Experiments and Algorithms" at 5G PPP ICT-52 Workshop on 6G by G. Iosifidis (TU DELFT)
5G PPP webinar	"DAEMON: Reliable RAN Virtualization in Shared Platforms" at 5G PPP ICT-52 Workshop on 6G by A. Garcia Saavedra (NEC)
5G PPP webinar	"DAEMON: Learning to Predict for Automated Network Management" at 5G PPP ICT-52 Workshop on 6G by A. Collet (IMDEA/UC3M)
5G PPP Whitepaper	"The 6G Architecture Landscape - European perspective" by Marco Gramaglia (UC3M)
5G PPP Whitepaper	"European Vision for the 6G Network Ecosystem" by Marco Fiore (IMDEA)
5G PPP Whitepaper	"Beyond 5G/6G KPIs and Target Values" by Vangelis Kosmatos and Andres Garcia Saavedra (WINGS, NEC)

2.3 Exploitation Activities

2.3.1 Standardization Activities

This section reports the SDO achievements on the standardization contributions that have been approved in the lifetime of the project made by the project related to the DAEMON innovations and use cases. So far, we have obtained in total 39 approved contributions across O-RAN, IETF/IRTF, ETSI and 3GPP, and ITU-T SDOs, as summarized in the following table, Table 6.

Table 6. Summary of DAEMON SDO Activities, from the start of the project to the end of Y2.

SDO	WG	Partner	#Contributions	Type of Contributions
ORAN	WG2 WG3	NEC NBL	19	Non-RT RIC and near-RT RIC architectural design extensions
ETSI RIS	RIS ISG	NEC	11	RIS support: scenarios, use cases and corresponding requirements
IETF/IRTF	NMRG	TID	2	Published RFC 9316 on the concept of network intents; IRTF drafts on Digital Twin Network: Concepts and Reference Architecture
ETSI NFV	NFV ISG	TID	1	Contributions to the NFV ISG conversations based on the work we have performed in WP3/WP4 related to the intelligent approach of the virtual function placement within the environment of an operator.
ETSI ZSM	ZSM ISG	TID	1	Network Digital Twin work item
3GPP	SA2	NBL	2	Study on XR (Extended Reality) and media services
ITU-T	FG-AN	UC3M	2	NI use cases definition
ITU-T	FGAI4AD-01	ZSCALE	1	Automated driving safety data protocol – Specification. Automated Driving Safety Data using the Eclipse Zenoh protocol.

Among all the contributions, we got approved in O-RAN the most, which is more relevant to DAEMON research activities and innovations related to NIS. More specifically, the contributions to O-RAN are mainly focused on identifying the gaps of the current O-RAN architecture in both non-RT and near-RT RICs to support the needs and functionalities of the designed innovations and NIs from DAEMON, and accordingly, we proposed extensions to refine the O-RAN architecture and interfaces so as to enable the implementation of these NI functions in DAEMON.

In addition to O-RAN, we have also made significant contributions to ETSI ISG on Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS) in several work times on defining scenarios, use cases, and corresponding requirements on RIS modes, active and passive RISs, hybrid ones, also on power consumption, frequency selection, spectral efficiency enhancement, and beam management, etc. RIS has received increasing attention and has become one of the new radio technologies to enhance the RAN coverage for 6G. Thus, how to smartly manage the RIS is also a relevant field for DAEMON to extend the NI to the RIS domain.

In other SDOs, we have achieved one published RFC 9316 on defining network intents for intent-based network management systems and working on one IRTF draft on network digital twins, and besides, we have made a few contributions to ETSI, mainly to NFV and ZSM on network digital twin. It is also worth mentioning that we are currently working on preparing a Proof-of-Concept on Anomaly detection for ETSI ENI ISG in 2023. And we also made two contributions to 3GPP on 5GS to support XR (Extended Reality) and media enhancements. Within these two contributions, several potential approaches to apply packet marking to new Low-Latency, Low-Loss, and Scalable throughput (L4S) traffic in the mobile network are described. And such new L4S traffic will be studied in the application-aware RAN technology work conducted in WP3. In addition, two contributions in ITU-T were approved on NI use cases and specifications for automated driving use cases. Last but not least, we have regularly reported the SDO contributions to the pre-Std WG SDO impact report under 5G-PPP and 6G-IA.

Table 7 provides a detailed list of all approved SDO contributions during the second year of the project in 2022. The SDO contributions achieved in Y1 have already been reported in D6.2 [1], and thus are not repeated in this table.

Table 7. DAEMON SDO approved contributions during Y2.

Target SDO	Type of Contribution (Date)	Partner	WG	Contribution Descriptions	Rations to the related DAEMON Innovations and use cases
O-RAN	Standard contribution (Feb. 09 2022)	NEC	ORAN WG2 Non-RT-RIC	CR0010: O1 related data collection procedures based on data subscription	DAEMON innovations on non-RT RIC specifies the requirement for data collection procedure defined in this contribution.
O-RAN	Standard contribution (Feb. 09 2022)	NEC	ORAN WG2 Non-RT-RIC	CR0011: O2 related data collection procedures based on data subscription	DAEMON innovations on non-RT RIC specifies the requirement for data collection procedure defined in this contribution.
O-RAN	Standard contribution (January 13 2022)	NEC	ORAN WG3 Near-RT-RIC	CR0001: Abnormal Conditions in RIC Service Update procedure	DAEMON innovations related to anomaly detection contributes to the conditions for RIC service update.
O-RAN	Standard contribution (Feb 28 2022)	NEC	ORAN WG3 Near-RT-RIC	CR0002: Missing IE in RIC Control Failure	This contribution specifies the information to be sent by the E2 Node to inform the Near-RT RIC that the RIC CONTROL has failed to be executed, which is needed by related anomaly detection algorithms defined in DAEMON.
O-RAN	Standard contribution (March 08 2022)	NEC	ORAN WG3 Near-RT-RIC	CR0003: Correction of wrong parameters and reference in DRB QoS Configuration.	Upon receiving the RIC Control Request, the E2 node shall invoke procedures related to DRB QoS Configuration, such as Bearer Context Management, UE Context Management, RRC Message Transfer, etc. This contribution corrects some of the QoS configurations, e.g., packet delay budget and packet error rate, based on DAEMON defined NI algorithms.
O-RAN	Standard contribution (Feb 23 2022)	NEC	ORAN WG2 Non-RT-RIC	CR 0012: The maximum number of PolicyType ID	This contribution is relevant for the non-RT RIC rApps to define the limits for

					how many policies that can be transferred in a single A1 message.
O-RAN	Standardization contribution (June/07/2022)	NEC	ORAN.WG2 Non-RT-RIC	<u>CR NEC-0015:</u> Subscribe to enforcement status of A1 policy changes	Adding a procedure for subscribing to the enforcement status of A1 policy changes as part of the A1 policy management services.
O-RAN	Standard contribution (May/13/2022)	NEC	ORAN WG2 Non-RT-RIC	<u>CR 0013:</u> Use cases for Data Management and Exposure Services	Defines the use case for a Data Consumer rApp to request data from the DME (Data management entity), needed by DAEMON rApps.
O-RAN	Standardization contribution (June/13/2022)	NEC	ORAN WG2 Non-RT-RIC	<u>CR 0016:</u> Use cases for Data Management and Exposure Services	Add the use case "The DME subscribes data from a Data Producer rApp", where such cases may be needed by DAEMON rApps.
O-RAN	Standardization contribution (May/13/2022)	NEC	ORAN WG2 Non-RT-RIC	<u>CR 0014:</u> Use cases for Data Management and Exposure Services	Addresses the use case to request data from a Data Producer rApp and adds description of the use case for data request between Data Producer rApp and Data management entity (DME).
O-RAN	Standard contribution (Sep/14/2022)	NEC	ORAN.WG2 Non-RT-RIC	<u>CR NEC-0024:</u> Enhance the precondition of data collection	Add data registration/discovery procedures to enhance the precondition of data collection.
O-RAN	Standardization contribution (Sep/12/2022)	NEC	ORAN WG2 Non-RT-RIC	<u>CR NEC-0023:</u> supported data delivery method in Register data type procedure	Non-RT RIC algorithms requires to specify Data Producers to communicate information about how the data are collected by the SMO/Non-RT RIC framework (e.g., collection periodicity, event-trigger conditions, push or pull, etc.).
IETF/IRTF	2022	TID	NMRG	RFC 9316 https://www.rfc-editor.org/info/rfc9316	This RFC discusses the concept of network intents and specifically highlights stakeholder perspectives of intent, methods to classify and encode

					intent, and the associated intent taxonomy. It provides a foundation for intent-related research and solution development in DAEMON.
IETF/IRTF	2022	TID	NMRG	IRTF drafts: Digital Twin Network: Concepts and Reference Architecture https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/draft-irtf-nmr-network-digital-twin-arch/	Provide an overview of the concepts of Digital Twin Networks, provide the basic definitions and a reference architecture, lists a set of application scenarios, and discuss the benefits and key challenges of such technology.
ETSI NFV	2022	TID	NFV ISG	Available at the ETSI NFV technology pages: https://docbox.etsi.org/ISG/NFV/Open/Other/NFV_Research_Agenda-202104.pdf	TID has a leadership role in ETSI NFV (as part of the Network Operator Council), where they oversee the research agenda, as well as make contributions to the working documents.
ETSI ZSM	2022	TID	ZSM ISG	Network Digital Twin work item: DGR/ZSM-015_Nwk_DTwin https://portal.etsi.org/webapp/WorkProgram/Report_WorkItem.asp?WKI_ID=64372	This work item discusses the Network Digital Twin concept, investigates its applicability for automation of zero-touch network and service management and introduces existing, emerging and future scenarios, which DAEMON has considered.
3GPP	2022	NBL	SA2	3GPP TR 23.700-60	Provide a study on XR (Extended Reality) and media services based on the application-aware RAN technology work in WP3.
3GPP	2022	NBL	SA2	S2-2207784: Conclusions for Key issue#3: 5GS information exposure for XR/media Enhancements	In this contribution, several approaches to applying packet marking to new Low-Latency, Low-Loss, and Scalable throughput (L4S) traffic in the mobile network are described. And such new L4S traffic will be studied in the application-aware

					RAN technology work conducted in WP3.
ITU-T	2022	ZSCALE	FGAI4AD-01	Automated driving safety data protocol – Specification.	Automated Driving Safety Data using the Eclipse Zenoh protocol. https://unece.org/sites/default/files/2023-01/GRVA-15-12a1e.pdf
ETSI	2022	NEC	RIS ISG	Created a RIS work item (WI): DGR/RIS-001 https://portal.etsi.org/webapp/WorkProgram/ReportWorkItem.asp?WKI_ID=63938	NEC is the funding member of ISG on Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS) and as well rapporteur of this WI. This WI is about scenarios, use cases and corresponding requirements. So far, in total 6 revisions (contributions) have been made by NEC to refine the use scenarios, use cases and corresponding requirements for RIS deployment.
ETSI	2022	NEC	RIS ISG	RIS(22)TM02004 “Preliminaries on DGR/RIS-001 (GR)”	Contribution to the definition of RIS, and added a new subsection on RIS Operating Frequency, also new use cases have been added (Spectral Efficiency Enhancement and Beam Management Enhancements).
ETSI	2022	NEC	RIS ISG	RIS(22)TM03013 “TP to DGR/RIS-001 on active and passive RISs”	This contribution is related to RIS types in terms of power consumption, providing clarifications on the definition of active or passive RISs. The definition of RIS types follows the analysis and descriptions in a recently available survey paper as well as aligned with DAEMON scenarios on RIS.
ETSI	2022	NEC	RIS ISG	RIS(22)TM03014 “TP to DGR 001 on RIS Modes”	The contribution is related to RIS modes. The definition of RIS models is also considered in some early work on RIS in DAEMON.

ETSI	2022	NEC	RIS ISG	RIS(22)004011, "hardware_desig n_RIS_001"	The concept of Hybrid RIS has been introduced in this contribution, which may be considered for some RIS deployment scenarios.
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2.3.2 Open-Source Activities

This section outlines the relevant open-source projects being leveraged in the DAEMON project, as well as the work that has been completed with respect to these projects during Y2.

2.3.2 Relevant Open-Source Projects

This section presents the open-source activities used or contributed to by the DAEMON project.

2.3.2.1.1 *srsRAN*

The SRS software radio suite (srsRAN) provides an open-source, flexible and robust framework for 5G network R&D, prototype development, and real-world deployment. The suite provides complete UE and RAN applications and is widely used for mobile wireless R&D in both academia and industry. Recognized for its stability, performance, and code quality, srsRAN has provided the foundation for a broad range of successful R&D projects, featuring as a key tool in more than 200 peer-reviewed articles [2]. On the GSMA mobile security hall of fame [3], srsRAN has been leveraged by researchers in many of the most recent Coordinated Vulnerability Disclosures (CVDs).

Under DAEMON, SRS will provide complete 5G RAN and UE solutions which can be leveraged, modified, and extended to develop and demonstrate the AI-enabled Network Intelligence envisaged by the project.

DAEMON modifications and extensions will be developed by SRS in coordination with partners and contributed to the main code base where possible. Other modifications may be made by specific partners for certain use cases. In some instances, it may not be possible to make these available to the public by contributing them back to the srsRAN GitHub repository. Contributions to the srsRAN project from DAEMON may come in the form of small features (such as bug fixes) or larger features (such as O-RAN compliant interfaces). So far, DAEMON has been responsible for the addition of multiple bug fixes to the srsRAN code base, which has been highlighted as a result of work done in the project.

2.3.2.1.2 *Eclipse*

The Eclipse Foundation, specifically the Edge Native Working Group initiative, fosters openly accessible solutions for Edge and Fog computing and has taken a major lead in this domain. It provides Open-Source edge computing platforms to solve the complex challenges in decentralized environments at the mobile network edge. ZSCALE, a partner in DAEMON, is a founder and steering member of the Edge Native Working Group.

Under DAEMON, ZSCALE provided a release for the Eclipse Zenoh v0.7.0-rc release candidate on December 22, 2022, and it is available in the official repository [4]. ZSCALE has actively participated in different events of Eclipse IoT and Eclipse Edge, like EclipseCon 2022, Eclipse IoT, and Edge Day 2022, and contributed to the 2022 IoT and Edge Developer Survey Results [5].

2.3.2 Activities during Y2

The second year of the project has brought many technical innovations and advancements to the targeted areas of NI. As a result, DAEMON has made five contributions to open-source projects in Y2. These contributions were made to Zenoh-flow and the Eclipse Zenoh release 0.6.0-beta, and srsRAN. These are outlined in Table 8. This brings the total open-source contributions made by the project to five. This is slightly just ahead of the projected four contributions to open-source projects by the end of Y2. The project is expected to make six open-source contributions in total, to meet the planned KPIs.

NI-assisted functionalities developed as part of the project, specifically within WP4, require memory and a stable platform to ensure they can be utilized in the most efficient manner. With this, SRS sought to make srsRAN a more stable platform with which to test the NI-assisted functionalities of the project, focusing specifically on the memory usage of the scheduler and the stability connections between network elements. The work being done in the project led to a memory leak in the NR scheduler within the eNB being highlighted, as well as a potential bottleneck in the S1AP and SCTP connection between the RAN and the core.

The memory leak was addressed in srsRAN 22.10, resulting in a more efficient and less memory-intensive implementation of srsENB. In turn, this would free up more memory in the computing hardware for other

applications. Within the scope of DAEMON, this frees up more memory for NI-functionality and NI-assisted functions.

Changes to how the S1 interface is established and maintained between srsENB and the core network were also added in srsRAN 22.10. In particular, changes were made to the S1AP implementation to remove a potential for message blocking between the RAN and core. This was done by configuring the S1AP threads to only run in the background. In addition to this, a configurable timer was added to the srsENB configuration file, which enables srsENB to automatically re-start the S1 establishment procedure if a connection fails or cannot be established on the first attempt. This helps to create a more stable RAN implementation, as connection failures between srsENB and the core are made less likely to occur.

Table 8. DAEMON Open-source Contributions during Y2.

Type	Overview	Date	Open-source Project	Partner
Commit	Contribution to Zenoh-flow to provide boilerplates for Python and C++ nodes	15/04/2022	Zenoh-Flow	ZSCALE
Commit	Contribution to Zenoh-flow to optionally toggle parts of a data flow using flags	18/05/2022	Zenoh-Flow	ZSCALE
Release	Contribution to Eclipse Zenoh release 0.6.0-beta1	30/09/2022	Zenoh	ZSCALE
Release	srsRAN 22.10 - Allow non-blocking S1AP connect and expose various other SCTP options	11/14/2022	srsRAN	SRS
Release	srsRAN 22.10 - Fix memleak in NR scheduler	11/14/2022	srsRAN	SRS

2.3.3 Academic Activities

During Y2, we continued with the academic activities that we had previously started during Y1 of the project. We further detail these activities in Table 9 below.

Table 9. Academic Activities during Y2.

Type	Title	University
MSc Thesis	Online Learning for Edge Network Caching	TU Delft
PhD Thesis	Optimization Algorithms for Robust Network Intelligence	TU Delft
PhD Thesis	Energy-efficient tasks assignment for heterogeneous deployment architectures on Edge Computing	UMA
PhD Thesis	Achieving Energy Efficiency with a Software Product Line Engineering Approach	UMA
PhD Thesis	Network intelligence for resource management in 6G networks	IMDEA, UC3M
PhD Thesis	Tailoring machine learning for zero-touch network and service management	IMDEA, UC3M
PhD Thesis	Integration and demonstration of remote sensing functionalities in future-generation mobile network architectures	IMDEA, UC3M
Postdoc	Design and implementation of network intelligence in the user plane of 6G mobile networks	IMDEA
Postdoc	Tailoring of Artificial Intelligence models for network orchestration	IMDEA
MSc Course	5G Standards	UC3M
MSc Course	B5G Operation Requirements	TU Delft

2.3.4 Industrial Exploitation Activities

DAEMON defined a series of performance metrics (Table 10) to use throughout the lifetime of the project to capture its status in terms of exploitation of the work. We previously extended the set of KPIs to include the three last rows, which speak toward the overall innovation activity in DAEMON. Out of these, we have already achieved two of them.

Furthermore, we had previously adjusted the exploitation plan to address the potential interaction with the Innovation Radar. Our goal was to select for submission to the Innovation Radar several innovations from the set of new methods, tools, systems, services and processes supporting NI service provisioning. We have over-passed the target that we have set for ourselves and identified five different innovations

that have already been accepted and published by the Innovation Radar, which we further detail in Table 12. With this, we have thus over-achieved the key exploitation metric regarding the “Number of new methods, tools, systems, services and processes supporting NI services provision”.

Regarding the “Number of commercially available and exploitable DAEMON NI tools and methods”, we have also achieved this target, as two of the five DAEMON innovations in the Innovation Radar have a market maturity of “Tech Ready”. This means that three innovations are progressing in the technology development process (e.g., pilots, prototypes, demonstration).

Table 10. Key Exploitation Metrics.

KPI	Target	Relevant Initiatives for Target
Submitted contributions to standards	10	3GPP, ETSI, O-RAN, ITU, ONF, IETF
Patent applications	7	Contributions in the main innovation areas DAEMON targets.
Open-source contributions	3	srsRAN (formerly srsLTE), Eclipse Zenoh
Participation in industry events	3	MWC, IWPC, etc.
Demonstrators	2	Radio, Orchestration, Management, Edge
Organized industrial workshops	1	Over 30 attendees each
Number of new business models developed to support native NI via DAEMON	1	Innovation in the business category
Number of commercially available and exploitable DAEMON NI tools and methods	2	Patented innovation tools and/or methods under exploitation within a business unit
Number of new methods, tools, systems, services and processes supporting NI services provision	3	The main areas of innovation aim to address map to the NI-assisted functionalities addressed by DAEMON

Furthermore, during this second year, DAEMON has also filed three additional patent applications (which we detail in Table 11) in addition to the ones previously filed during Y1.

2.3.4 Patents

During Y2, DAEMON submitted three patent applications related to technical activities in WP3 and WP4.

Table 11. DAEMON patent applications during Y2.

Patent title	Owner	Sector	Market/Stakeholder	Status
Reinforcement Learning-based method for automatic distributed optimization of cellular networks	TID	Industry	Telco	Filed
Unsupervised clustering approach for identifying device patterns and requirements for network orchestration	TID	Industry	Telco	Filed
A method to mitigate the noisy neighbours problem in vRAN deployments configuring the different units' placement and its functional split	NEC	Industry	5G	Filed

2.3.4 Innovation Radar

DAEMON generated five main innovations which were already included in the Innovation Radar,¹ which we report in Table 12. All innovation were published in the Innovation Radar during Y2 and correspond to project activities both within WP3 and WP4. These innovations demonstrate the potential of the project to impact the technology landscape and fill the gap around the need for network intelligence functionalities. The five innovations correspond to different areas that we identified and cover in DAEMON and guarantee the impact of the project beyond its termination.

¹ <https://www.innoradar.eu/>

Table 12. DAEMON Innovations included in the Innovation Radar.

ID	Innovation name	Partner	Innovation Status	Innovation Type	Level of Innovation	Exploitation Strategy
1	ANCHOR: Anomaly Detection Approach for the Roaming Platform ²	TID	Under Development	New product	Very innovative	Only deployed as new to the organization/company (new internal processes implemented, etc.)
2	Reliable DU design suitable for virtualization ³	NEC	Under Development	New product	Obviously innovative and easily appreciated advantages to customer	Introduced as new to the market (commercial exploitation)
3	A Reconfigurable Intelligent Surface-based system to manage multiple wired connections in data centers ⁴	NEC	Under Development	New product	Obviously innovative and easily appreciated advantages to customer	Introduced as new to the market (commercial exploitation)
4	Compute-aware RAN orchestrator (O-RAN Non-RT RIC differentiator) ⁵	NEC	Under Development	New product	Obviously innovative and easily appreciated advantages to customer	Introduced as new to the market (commercial exploitation)
5	Classifier for video, data, gaming traffic ⁶	NBL	Under Development	Significantly improved product	Obviously innovative and easily appreciated advantages to customer	Introduced as new to the market (commercial exploitation)

2.3.5 Events

2.3.5 Infocom World Conference

The latest **24th Infocom World Conference** that has been held physically in Athens, Greece, on November 29-30, 2022, (<https://infocomworld.gr/>) has been considered “the greatest ICT & Media Conference in South-Eastern Europe” and it is widely regarded as “the major annual Meeting of all the digital market stakeholders” in order to implement digital transformation, conformant to current market needs and related challenges and especially contributing to the effort for creating a fully digital Greece.

Figure 12. Infocom World Conference 2022 website landing page.

The Infocom World Conference 2022, following a successful tradition of 24 subsequent years, has been about the revolutionary effects coming from the deployment of “Fiber and 5G Highways” in Greece.

² <https://www.innoradar.eu/innovation/46063>

³ <https://www.innoradar.eu/innovation/46064>

⁴ <https://www.innoradar.eu/innovation/46062>

⁵ <https://www.innoradar.eu/innovation/46061>

⁶ <https://www.innoradar.eu/innovation/46060>

As digital transformation evolves into a “key pillar” of growth for multiple aspects of our modern economy, deployment of appropriate network infrastructures capable of serving fast data transfer becomes a critical objective for further progress, especially due to the fact that such digital “highways” will also support the corresponding transformation of public and private sectors. This rapid digitization process is expected not only to strengthen the digital-based economy at all levels but will also offer new “paths” for business and opportunities for growth. This, however, implicates an effective and wide deployment of the necessary connectivity infrastructures (especially 5G) that are required for highly innovative services and/or corresponding applications.

In this context, market actors – and particularly the telecommunications operators – are making increased investments in developing 5G and fiber infrastructure worldwide. Taking these trends into account, we are, after all, at a time when large and important multinationals are choosing Greece for the development of their own hubs – whether it is data centers that serve the wider region or technology and product development centers or hubs that strengthen the human resource skills. Thus, a reliable telecommunications infrastructure with state-of-the-art technology will not only strengthen the operation of such centers but will also attract new investments, making Greece a “hub for hubs”. Within the core objectives of the Infocom World Conference 2022 have been the way how Fiber and 5G are changing the market and offering new opportunities for the involved market players, with the aim of creating an innovation ecosystem for investments and growth.

DAEMON had a strong presence with a booth in the main exhibition centre of Infocom World 2022, organized by OTE. This can be seen in Figure 13.

Figure 13. DAEMON booth at Infocom World 2022.

2.3.5 EuCNC 2022

EuCNC 2022 (the European Conference on Networks and Communications) was held alongside the 6G Summit in Grenoble, France. Both are top European conferences in the area of communication networks, EuCNC is supported by the European Commission, and the 6G Summit originates from the 6G Flagship program in Finland.

After two years of online meetings due to the global pandemic, the 2022 conference was held physically in the city of Grenoble, known internationally as a leading hub for microelectronics and digital technologies. The organizers wanted to highlight the importance of semiconductor technologies and applications for European technological sovereignty and cybersecurity, something that can also be seen in the European Chips Act recently proposed by the Commission by choosing this location.

Telecommunications were at the forefront of discussions at the conference, from 5G deployment and mobile IoT, to 6G exploration. Future communications systems were considered and tested through experimentation and testbeds, with over 1500 delegates, researchers, and stakeholders from more than 40 countries participating. Innovations in the field of applications and services were also presented.

DAEMON had a strong presence with a booth in the main exhibition centre, as shown in Figure 14, Figure 15, and Figure 16. During the event, five partners and eight persons from the DAEMON consortium participated by showing three demos.

- NI for Edge orchestration: The demo tested and validated the impact of NI on the edge orchestration in a realistic Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) environment. It includes an AI-enhanced multi-layer orchestration system (edge & cloud), including reinforcement learning and multi-agent reinforcement learning. It demonstrates a Smart Highway testbed with edge computing nodes and vehicles for real-work application deployments. Zenoh was used for location-transparent data engineering.

- Nuberu: Reliable RAN virtualization: Nuberu is a Distributed Unit (DU) design that is not affected by computing fluctuations in shared platforms. It acts as an enabler for a series of predictive NI mechanisms that let us protect critical tasks and attain 100% reliability guarantees. A preliminary prototype has been built and demonstrated on top of srsRAN.
- Federated Learning powered Anomaly Detection in B5G/6G: The proposed solution utilizes Federated Learning algorithms and mechanisms during the anomaly detection process in B5G/6G to achieve higher performance compared with the current approaches of anomaly detection: centralized and distributed. The deployment is realized using a set of Linux containers that emulates gNBs and UEs and in which the federated learning clients and controller are deployed.

In addition, **the DAEMON project was highlighted by the Technology Leadership Officer of NOKIA** Mikael Rylander during his keynote presentation at the opening of the EuCNC programme, as seen in Figure 17.

Figure 14. DAEMON Booth at EuCNC2022 (1).

Figure 15. DAEMON Booth at EuCNC2022 (2).

Figure 16. DAEMON Booth at EuCNC2022 (3).

Figure 17. DAEMON highlighted by NOKIA Technology Leadership Officer.

3 Communication Plan for Year 3

H2020 DAEMON continues in the third year with the set of necessary presentation materials targeted for various audience types. Our communication plan includes using a *package* to promote the project, as well as *activities for the general public, students and prospective researchers*. The following table, Table 13, includes the targeted audience, the related activities, the timing, and the metrics of the communication activities, including quantified goals.

Table 13. H2020 DAEMON communication plan.

Audience	Activity	Timing	Metric
All, General public, Research	Project website. DAEMON shares its concepts, results and achievements through its dedicated project website. The website is dynamically synchronized with DAEMON's social network accounts and is the primary tool of communication and promotion of it.	Cont. update	Google, Twitter, Facebook, and Zenodo Analytics, and Advanced Page Visit Counter readings. That includes country of access, number of unique visits per page, total number of visits, prints, and retention. We aim to keep the minimum of 75% of the audience coming from countries outside the consortium.
All, General public	Press releases, posters, leaflets. DAEMON prepares and distributes project posters, press releases and leaflets to raise public awareness.	Event-driven	Updated leaflets and posters. Published press releases (target: at least two per year. Assets with open access DOIs published in Zenodo with certain metrics as number of online reads and downloads, as well as Twitter prints of the DOI.
General public	Public Communication. DAEMON project, including its impact on the transformation of vertical industry, is regularly promoted through participation and organization of events for society at large and distribution through social media. We also make use of EC communication tools and magazines.	Event-driven	Num. of events organized / attended (target: at least one org. per year) Assets with open access DOIs published in Zenodo with certain metrics as number of online reads and downloads. Likewise, Twitter visualizations.
All, General public, Research	Social Networks. DAEMON is present on the main social network with official profiles and project pages. DAEMON social network profiles gradually advertise all outputs from all the work packages, including WP6. Additionally, these profiles constantly inform by short feeds of the main results and events from DAEMON and collaborators.	Cont. update	Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn and Instagram analytics, including number of likes, re-publishing, prints, and number and types of comments.
General public, Interest groups	Video. DAEMON has already created public videos to advertise the proposed network scenarios and their capabilities. New videos will be created focused on research outcomes and demo activities.	Event-driven	Videos of all demo activities available in the web, its Youtube channel, and Zenodo (open access DOIs). Number of likes, views and downloads.

Students	Lecture materials related with DAEMON are introduced in academic courses and webinars taught by partners	Potentially every 6 months	Number of related courses where project topics are introduced
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4 Dissemination Plan for Year 3

Dissemination and Collaboration activities are already conducted since Year 1 to help promote the project concept and results to the large European and International R&D community and raise opportunities for synergy with other projects and activities. This section presents the continuation of the plan in Year 2 into Year 3 and reports the achievements for dissemination and collaboration activities. In this section, we briefly summarize our overall dissemination plan for year 3.

- **Publications** in selected journals and magazines, such as IEEE/ACM journals, transactions and magazines, and reputed international conferences.
- **Collaborations** with EU and other national and international research projects through 5G-PPP working groups, networkd2020, and other H2020 projects in support of the 5G-PPP commitments and towards the realization of the B5G vision.
- **Presentations** and participation on behalf of the project in research-oriented workshops, industry-oriented workshops, technology platforms, and any other similar forum, including participation on academic and industrial panels organized in these events. In Year 2 we gave more emphasis to industrial events, and this continues for Year 3.
- Participation in public **exhibitions and demonstrations** for academia and industry to disseminate research work to create awareness of DAEMON technology and applications.
- **Organization of events**, such as tutorials and/or workshops, collocated with well-established conferences.

In general terms, DAEMON openly publishes most of its results and assets, whether they are more related to research and industry (e.g., papers, datasets) or to public communications (e.g., slides, general documents). They will keep having an open-access DOI, optimizing citations and/or re-usability of our results and supporting the freedom of sharing DAEMON results while avoiding limits to knowledge distribution. The resources will be hosted in Zenodo, the general-purpose open-access repository developed under the European OpenAIRE program and operated by CERN. Hence, the main Daemon project and resources indexer is OpenAIRE – an H2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 777541. The workflow was presented in detail in D6.1.

4.1 Dissemination Work Plan

The dissemination activities will be steered towards generating impact through peer-reviewed publications, presentations, talks, demonstrations, panels, workshops, and events. We plan to accomplish at least the same goals set for Year 3, including:

- Additional submission of at least 20 scientific articles for publication at reputed conferences and journals by Year 3.
- Additional submission to accomplish at least 30 contributions to SDOs, such as 3GPP, IETF, ETSI, IEEE, and ITU, over the lifetime of the project.
- Additional submission of at least two joint scientific documents/articles/publications for publication at reputed conferences and journals together with EU and international research projects, e.g., through 5G-PPP working groups or working groups of other platforms, such as networkd2020).
- Additional demonstrations of project-related prototypes or solutions at least one flagship event (e.g., MWC / EUCNC) in Year 3. This includes a merged prototype that integrates several DAEMON assets.
- Organization of at least 1 research- or industry-oriented workshop in year 3.
- Participation in at least 1 research- or industry-oriented workshop in year 3.
- Participation in at least 1 open-source project over the lifetime of the project.
- Filing at least 20 patent applications over the lifetime of the project.
- Addition of core skills for technology development within the project into academic curriculums, along with the proposal of PhD and MSc theses on specific topics on the DAEMON research agenda.

The following table, Table 14, summarizes the Y2 dissemination plan.

Table 14. H2020 DAEMON dissemination plan.

Audience	Activity	Timing	Metric
Academic and industrial research	DAEMON aims at publishing its work in selected, high impact-factor journals and magazines on communications and networking (e.g., IEEE Communication Magazine, IEEE JSAC), and reputed international conferences (e.g., ICC, Mobicom, Globecom, CoNEXT, EUCNC). An appropriate balance between academic and industrial awareness is considered.	Continuous.	At least 20 publications per year in top-tier scientific journals and conferences.
Other research projects	Collaboration with other EU and international research projects (e.g., through 5G-PPP working groups, or working groups of other platforms, such as network2020) will also be key towards a coordinated action inside the 5G-PPP and with other H2020 projects related with the design of B5G technologies.	5G-PPP WGs & ad hoc bi-lateral collaboration.	Num. of meetings attended (target: at least two per year). Num. of joint documents generated (target: at least two per year).
Mostly academia, but also industry	Organization, presentations and participation in the organization of events (e.g., panels, targeted workshops, workshops co-located with relevant conferences, special sessions) and participation as keynote speaker, panelist, etc., thanks to important vendors, technology providers and operators, high-tech SMEs, and reputed academic organizations within the consortium.	Participation in one event per year One workshop organized.	Organization of one 30-people workshop co-located with a major conference (e.g., EUCNC, IEEE WCNC, ICC, INFOCOM) with 70% satisfaction in the workshop quality poll for attendees. Participation in workshops: we measure the number of events (target: at least one per year), we will measure the metrics (web access, cites) of work presented to assess its impact.
Industry	Exploitation workshop. Chaired by the innovation manager and specifically devoted to maximizing the exploitation outcomes of the project in terms of standardization, patenting/licensing, and products and services. It will involve experts on innovation from the various companies representing all industrial sectors already in the project (verticals, operators, vendors, and SMEs) and external experts acting as advisors on maximizing the exploitation outcome of the project.	Two workshops organized before M36.	One 30-people exploitation workshop in the first half of Y3, and a second in the second half of Y3, both with 70% satisfaction in the poll for attendees.
Mostly industry, but also academia	Technology demonstration. The project team believes that the realization of proofs-of-concept is the key to maximize innovation potential. DAEMON will participate in demonstrations of key project components in exhibition booths in fairs, such as those of EUCNC, or industrial events, such as Mobile World Congress (MWC), where some of partners have regularly exhibited.	Approximately at every 6 months.	Technology demonstration in at least two events per year. More demonstrations in several events are targeted.

Industry	Though being part of exploitation activities, the participation in standardization efforts of DAEMON also offers an indirect way to disseminate the results of the project to the industrial community. Nevertheless, there are other non-traditional ways of standardizing (e.g., OPNFV, OpenStack) , such as contributing and publishing open-source software (part of the DAEMON exploitation plan), which may become a de facto standard.	Continuous meetings Participation in at least one open-source project.	Participation in at least one open-source project.
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4.2 Synergies with Other Projects for Y3

Over the course of Y3, DAEMON plans to continue its synergies with other projects.

Firstly, the project will also continue its engagement with multiple 5GPPP boards and working groups via partners in the consortium. We have plans to lead the writing or contribute to several white papers and books edited in the context of the 5G PPP entities.

In addition, the project has plans to reinforce collaborations with other 5G PPP projects in multiple forms in Y3. Specifically, the project already has several planned events and ongoing engagements that involve tight cooperation with other 5G PPP projects at flagship events like the Mobile World Congress (MWC) and the IEEE ICC and EUCNC conferences, all happening in 2023.

MWC 2023 will take place Between February 27th and March 2nd. DAEMON will have a joint booth at the conference with AI@EDGE, another H2020 project. Sharing a booth will be an opportunity to foster a working relationship between the projects and showcase to attendees of MWC the synergies between the concepts driving the two actions. This event will also provide a major platform to demo some of the key advancements and features of the DAEMON project to an audience including some of the main industrial players in B5G and 6G ecosystems. DAEMON plans to show two demos at MWC: one from WINGS and IMEC, and one from IMDEA. MWC is a much more commercially focused conference compared to some of the others the project has attended during Y1 and Y2, so this will provide a good opportunity to expand the reach and knowledge of the project within the industry.

IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC) is one of two IEEE Communications Society's flagship conferences. The 2023 edition of ICC will take place between May 28th and June 1st. Here, DAEMON will take contribute to a technical talk at the 6G-IA workshop organized by 5G PPP actors since DAEMON's proposal for a talk was accepted by the workshop organizers in late 2022. The project plans to present the Network Intelligence Orchestrator (NIO) at this talk, which will also be demoed at the venue. The demo will show the first version of the NIO. A booth at the conference is also planned, possibly again in collaboration with AI@EDGE.

The final currently planned event (as of the submission time of this deliverable) is a presence at **EUCNC 2023**. The event will take place from June 6th to June 9th. The project plans to hold a workshop in collaboration with at least one of AI@EDGE, the 5G PPP Technical Board, or Hexa-X and Hexa-XII. Proposals are currently ongoing. Plans are in place for this to be an industrial workshop, with potential speakers from industry leaders and SMEs. A booth is also planned, which will allow the project to present more demos outlining the work in DAEMON.

Other options to cooperate with other projects will be explored as they arise. The project will continue to explore all possible avenues of collaboration with other projects during Y3 and after the completion of the project. It is hoped that by doing so, the success of the project can be guaranteed long after the end of the project.

5 Exploitation Plan for Year 3

During the final year of the project, DAEMON puts forward an ambitious exploitation plan aimed at ensuring the impact of the work we have been carrying out so far, with the target of ensuring its significance and importance beyond the end of the project. With hopefully a more mature understanding of the gaps and needs of the market, we aim to assess how DAEMON's innovations (corresponding to the many activities we have been reporting in D5.2) respond to the expectations of our stakeholders.

Regarding the key exploitation metrics we presented in Table 10, we will also work to achieve during Y3 the metric of "new business models developed to support native NI via DAEMON".

5.1 Products and Services

With five innovations already published in the Innovation Radar (see Table 12), our goal for Y3 is to move our focus towards conducting proof of concept validations with various stakeholders and showcasing the benefits of our tools. Out of the five innovations, two already reported "Tech Ready" market maturity, while three were in a market maturity level of "Exploration", meaning that we were exploring the value creation opportunities. During this final year of the project, we aim to further the market maturity level of the "exploratory" innovations and plan pilots, prototypes, and demonstration. In this sense, we are working towards reaching a market maturity of "Tech Ready" for at least an additional innovation. Of course, in DAEMON, we will not limit ourselves to the innovation already published in the Innovation Radar, but we will strive to find new opportunities in the large list of activities that we have reported in both WP3 and WP4.

In this section, we further detail the individual exploitation plans of the different partners within the consortium, which we break down per partner category.

5.1.1 Vendors and Service Providers

Vendors participating in DAEMON further commit to lead the future market of B5G technologies by developing novel hardware, software platforms, and services. Three timeframes were defined:

1. Short term – Opportunity to get their R&D efforts into focus and evolve their current product portfolio with vertical requirements as input.
2. Medium term – Use findings to understand verticals requirements and needs related to the various industrial markets and to identify gaps in 5G End-to-End connectivity platforms in order to develop innovative, flexible solutions for B5G systems
3. Long term – Exploitation of results by further feeding their product to business units.

Table 15. Exploitation plan for vendors and service providers.

Partner	Brief exploitation plan
NEC	The overall exploitation plan of NEC has not changed with respect to D6.2 [1]. In the medium term, the Activities A1, A2, A4 and A5 in the context of NI for sustainable virtualized RANs will be used as differentiators in NEC's vRAN product portfolio: A1 and A2 to improve the virtualization technologies used in NEC's DUs, and A4 and A5 to improve NEC's RAN Intelligent Control solutions. In the long term, Activity A23 will be used to open a new line of products in NEC on smart reflectors. In the short-term, NEC plans to file one additional patent application during Y3.
NBL	NBL's exploitation plan has not changed with respect to D6.2 [1]. In the medium term, the activity A3 will contribute to a planned PoC of an application-aware RAN (see item 5 in Table 12). In the long-term, activities A8 and A12 will contribute a self-learning MANO, and activities A6, A7 and A11, which concentrate on energy aspects and MEC (multi-access edge computing) aspects thereof, will contribute to the development of new features in related products (see Table 19).

5.1.2 Network Operators

Network operators will evaluate how to best fulfill the requirements and service portfolio of vertical industry over their network, as well as how to shape their relationship with them.

Table 16. Exploitation plan for network operators.

Partner	Brief exploitation plan
TID	The exploitation plan for year 3 of the project will follow the same guidelines adopted during year 2. TID aims at exploiting DAEMON's results jointly with the business and Telefonica's operation units as follows: (i) improve or develop new methods to operational assessment of network systems, (ii) derive innovative

	<p>products or services based on DAEMON technology, and (iii) submit patents to protect TID findings.</p> <p>Through internal innovation processes, TID will continue to test and deploy DAEMON AI-based solutions for anomaly detection in the big data platforms of linked stakeholders, including mobile operators such as O2 UK, as well as global platform operators, such as Telefonica Global Solutions Roaming platform. Specifically, we will continue our collaboration for deploying the solutions we developed in WP3 and WP4 to the corresponding business units, with a focus on deploying data processing pipelines and building trust between the network/platform operators and the NI functionalities we develop. TID will work together with the business units to run a proof-of-concept demo of the DAEMON technology for anomaly detection within their system.</p> <p>In the short term, TID plans to file one more patent application during Y3.</p>
OTE	<p>Continuing with the goals set out for previous years, OTE is highly interested in accelerating the development and deployment of modern and innovative NI functionalities developed in DAEMON. The modern and quite innovative features of the DAEMON findings may be able to influence, to a significant extent, future market-related policies by offering important advantages for a more effective usage either of existing or of planned -to be developed- facilities. The related DAEMON-based solutions may have dramatic effects on the market sector and this might be a beneficial advantage for the company, especially to offer competitive solutions that could facilitate the market transition towards a real environment. OTE considers the case of adopting part of the DAEMON implementations within their networks.</p> <p>Moreover, OTE already participated in the large industrial event Infocom World 2022, and will do so the next year, in order to inform the strategic partners of OTE & DT Group about the new DAEMON findings and investigate their potential adoption.</p>

5.1.3 Small and Medium Enterprises

SMEs plan to evolve their products in their specific fields of interest. Three time-frames were defined:

1. Short term – SMEs will exploit the technology created by DAEMON by contributing to open-source projects and training courses on SDN, NFV, MEC architectures, and cloud platforms.
2. Medium/Long term – SMEs could design novel concepts inspired by DAEMON results to feed back their product portfolio, which will foresee in the long term an increase in their competitiveness for consultancy services.

Table 17. Exploitation plan for small and medium enterprises.

Partner	Brief exploitation plan
ZSCALE	<p>ZSCALE seeks to exploit DEAMON innovations related to AI-based management applied to edge infrastructure and data-critical platforms. Specifically, the expected innovations of DAEMON will enable ZSCALE to augment its current intelligent computing platform for Edge Computing with more dynamic management of the resources and services provisioned at the Edge. ZSCALE seeks the transfer of the developed technologies by first fostering open-source projects to later build a complete value chain. Part of DAEMON innovations will be fed into the open-source project Eclipse Zenoh & Eclipse Zenoh-Flow, currently led by ZSCALE. The aim of Eclipse Zenoh is to provide a protocol suite for adaptive and distributed data-sharing, to enhance data distribution and flexibility. The aim of Eclipse Zenoh-flow is to provide a dataflow programming framework for computations that span from the cloud to the device enabling users to declare a dataflow graph that represents a set of nodes (sources, operators, or sinks) and linking them for dynamic load at run time.</p>
SRS	<p>SRS is an Irish SME providing full-stack SDR solutions for 4G and 5G systems. SRS UE and eNodeB/gNodeB stacks target x86, ARM, and FPGA hardware platforms, and our open, modular architecture support highly customized special-purpose systems. SRS adopts a unique business model that combines open-source and commercial licenses. Thanks to DAEMON, SRS will push forward its UE and gNodeB solutions, with a special focus on its new 5G SA gNB architecture, expanding and improving them for B5G systems. Specifically, the activities carried out in DAEMON will allow testing and strengthening of the SRS 5G product portfolio, supporting the company in the addition of new features and improved performance. On the one hand, this will benefit the overall R&D community, which uses SRS' open-source solutions; on the other hand, it will allow SRS to present new product offerings to its commercial partners, promoting and accelerating the development of SRS' B5G product suite.</p>

WINGS	WINGS is an SME that delivers solutions (software and hardware) for various verticals, namely for the areas: (1) environment (air quality/pollution, sea and land aspects), (2) networks and infrastructures (water/energy/gas, transportation, construction infrastructures); (3) production and manufacturing, which covers industry 4.0, logistics, aquaculture, and food safety; (4) service sectors, with an emphasis on health. The solutions rely on: (a) IoT devices with embedded intelligence, (b) advanced wireless connectivity, cloud, and big data platforms; (c) AI mechanisms; (d) visualization, which range from mobile applications and dashboards to AR/VR. WINGS has a range of products spanning several sectors, which include AI mechanisms, including anomaly detection as one of the main functionalities. In this direction, the federated learning based and anomaly detection solutions designed in WP4 and prototyped in WP5 will be integrated with the actual WINGS products targeting in improving the AI performance in terms of accuracy, resilience, robustness and trustworthiness. Through DAEMON, WINGS will enhance its AI competencies of its products compared to other SMEs in the market.
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5.1.4 Academic and Research Centers

The Universities and R&D centers participating in DAEMON are interested in building on and further developing existing research in the networking research community. Two timeframes were defined:

1. Short/Medium term – academia will improve the knowledge in 5G and B5G, multi-domain orchestration, and slicing, transferring it to the industry.
2. Medium/Long term – the patent and license rewards will help to undertake future European and international research, which will contribute towards further collaborative research possibilities with the project partners and others.

Table 18. Exploitation for academia and research centers.

Partner	Brief exploitation plan
IMDEA	The exploitation plan for year 3 of the project will follow the same guidelines adopted during year 2. Therefore, IMDEA keeps its commitment to support the transfer of technology to the industrial sector in order to improve its capacity for innovation and competitiveness, as well as to spin-off-companies in order to promote the release of new products and services to the global market. This will be pursued by seeking the transfer of the solutions developed in DAEMON into products through the wide network of collaborations that IMDEA has established with the telecommunication industry. DAEMON has in fact already supported the deployment of a new programmable network testbed at IMDEA consisting of three 32-port 100-Gbps Wedge programmable switches equipped with Barefoot Tofino chipsets and two Dell PowerEdge servers with 100-Gbps-capable interfaces used for emulation, monitoring and control purposes. The solutions developed and demonstrated using this hardware have been communicated to Intel (which manufactures the Tofino chipsets powering the switches); as a result, IMDEA has become part of the Intel Connectivity Research Program and of the Intel Connectivity Academy, and has obtained a donation by Intel within the Intel 2022 Fast Forward Initiative. All these initiatives have made IMDEA's research carried out within DAEMON highly visible at Intel. Finally, DAEMON has allowed IMDEA to recruit and train new PhD students and postdoctoral fellows, creating new expertise at the interface of machine learning and mobile networking critical to European industry.
IMEC	Similar to previous years, IMEC will keep exploring opportunities to exploit its R&D results during Year 3 via industrial affiliation programs, bilateral projects, IP transfer and licensing. The research carried out during the first two years as part of DAEMON has helped IMEC to start developing novel solutions of industrial value in wireless communications and AI applied on network management. The knowledge and expertise gained from DAEMON will be very relevant to extend IMEC's 5G test facilities, which are an important asset for both the research community and industrial partners. Specifically, we will continue the development and deployment of 5G networks in our testbeds (Smart HighWay) and performing new experimentation for edge orchestration (CityLab) with low-power AI. As IMEC IDLab is also embedded within the University of Antwerp, the knowledge gained from the project (e.g., beyond 5G networks, network intelligence, orchestration of intelligence, edge orchestration, low power AI) will be exploited to support advanced engineering master courses such as Topics in computer networks (https://www.uantwerpen.be/en/staff/miguel-camelo/education/?id=2022-2001WETTDC&lang=en&source=personal) and Internet of Things (https://www.uantwerpen.be/en/staff/miguel-camelo/education/?id=2022-

	2500WETINT&lang=en&source=personal) to train future computer scientist and electronic engineers.
UMA	<p>UMA keep having plans in year 3 to exploit the results of the DAEMON project, applying them to a new research project IRIS: Multi-Stage Configuration of Virtualized Services for Sustainable Adaptation of Mobile Networks, and other ongoing research projects RHEA: Language and Ecosystem for the Analysis, Derivation, Resolution and Materialization of Variability, and LEIA: Efficient Deployment of Augmented Reality Environments on the Edge. The DAEMON project gives us the opportunity to increase our knowledge of 5G technologies so that we can extend our energy efficient software solutions including the particularities of 5G networks. This will allow us to broaden the venues where to publish the research group results with top-rated conference and journals in the networks area. We also plan to continue our high publication rate in forums like SPL conference, and Information and Software Technology, Ad hoc networks or Future Generation of Computer Systems journals.</p> <p>On the other hand, the team at UMA has a strong relationship with many of the software companies located at the Andalusia Technology Part (http://www.pta.es/), and our participation in DAEMON will allow us to increase our visibility in the area of sustainable 5G solutions. We plan to contact some of these companies to invite them to contribute to the validation of the DAEMON project results in industrial environments. UMA will be in position to offer technical advice to companies about software sustainability in 5G/Edge/IoT environments, and offer the open-source results of the DAEMON to the network communication community.</p> <p>Regarding the academic activities at UMA, we expect to enrich existing Master courses about advance telecommunication networks and Telematics Engineering with the results of this project, and to offer tutorials, organize workshops and different teaching activities to disseminate the new expertise acquired under this project to the academic and industrial community in Malaga and Spain.</p>
UC3M	<p>UC3M plans to use the results of the DAEMON project mainly along three lines.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthen the academic leadership: thanks to the activities performed in DAEMON, UC3M will make its position in the scientific landscape on topics such as virtualized network functions, machine learning applied to networks, and network architecture design even stronger. UC3M will do that by publishing in top quality venues also leveraging the cooperation with other project's partners. • Foster the technology transfers to enterprises: many of the topics investigated by the project in general and by UC3M in particulars have the potential to become patents and products. One of the goals of UC3M is thus cooperate with other partners to achieve this goal as well as participate in main standardization groups to disseminate the UC3M work. • To consolidate the academic courses portfolio: UC3M seeks to consolidate the leading position in Spain among the best universities where to study computer science and telecommunication network engineering. Thanks to the participation in DAEMON, UC3M will be able to enhance the quality of the courses or even propose new masters together with the one already available such as the Big Data MSc, the 5G MSc, the SDN/NFV MSc, the Connected Industry 4.0 MSc, and the MSc in Telematics Engineering.
TUD	<p>For year 3, TU Delft's exploitation plans will adhere to the specifications defined in year 2 of the project. More precisely, the team of TU Delft aims to leverage the results of DAEMON in the following four ways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthen academic leadership: the research activities and the multifaceted collaboration activities with the partners of the project are expected to reinforce the academic profile of TUD in this area. Furthermore, we plan to leverage this opportunity in order to increase our research portfolio with problems that are related to next-generation mobile networks and with data-driven evaluation techniques for network orchestration algorithms. First-tier conference and journal venues will be targeted for publication of our results; while we plan to participate in the organization of conference workshops, special issues in journals, and tutorial lectures in relevant venues. • Technology transfer: we will explore potential venues for technology transfer, in collaboration with the industry partners of the consortium, but also with the locally-based enterprises and using the technology transfer program of TU Delft. • Funding Diversification: we will use the results and our experience in DAEMON to apply for additional funding, towards the end of its lifetime, in national funding agencies, and other suitable venues.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enrich relevant academic courses: the learning outcomes of DAEMON will feed existing courses that are organized in the Software Technology Department of TU Delft, but we will also explore the possibility of developing new courses entirely dedicated to and aligned with the mission of DAEMON (network intelligence algorithms and techniques).
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5.1.5 Exploitation Plan of Products and Platforms for Vendors and SMEs

In the following table, a detailed description of the platform and products for vendors and SMEs according to the exploitation plan is reported.

Table 19. Exploitation for vendors and SMEs.

Partner	Product / platform	Description of impact on platform/product	DAEMON innovation Area
NEC	NEC O-RAN product portfolio	NEC's RAN Intelligent Controllers for O-RAN Compatible RANs will be highly benefited with the outcome of DAEMON's research. The objective is to derive data collection and decision-making entities both at near-real-time and non-real-time timescales as a consequence of Activities A4 and A5.	RAN orchestration
	NEC 5G vRAN platform	NEC plans to exploit the results of Activities A1 and A2 to improve NEC's RAN virtualization platforms.	RAN virtualization
	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces	NEC will use the results of Activity A23 to open a new product line on smart reflectors	Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces
NBL	Digital Operations Center	The Digital Operations Center (DOC), which allows to expose the rich capabilities of a network as consumable services to tenants, will benefit from the DAEMON results. In particular, the techniques investigated in WP4 on self-learning MANO, i.e., on intelligent placement of VNFs and on cooperation of controllers operating at different timescales, will improve the service orchestration, service operations and service assurance algorithms of DOC.	End-to-end orchestrator
	CloudBand product family	The CloudBand (CB) product family, consisting of an NFV resource and network service orchestrator built for OpenStack and VMware, will be impacted by the DAEMON results. In particular, the activities placing VNFs and around scaling up/down and in/out, will be important to improve the algorithms that administer, monitor, and optimize NFV infrastructure resources across geographically distributed NFV infrastructure nodes. The results pertaining to the energy-aware placement and close-loop control are expected to impact the (future) list of features of the CloudBand product family.	End-to-end orchestrator
	FlowOne	The research carried out in DAEMON will allow enhancing FlowOne, which provides an agile and modular orchestration for managing service orchestration across virtualized and hybrid networks.	Edge orchestrator
WINGS	AIRWINGS	Product platform regarding Air Quality. It includes an AI component and is delivered over wireless infrastructure. AIRWINGS product will be impacted by the DAEMON results. In detail, the federated learning powered anomaly detection solution designed in WP4 and prototyped in WP5 will be integrated with the AI	Federated Learning powered Anomaly Detection

		algorithms developed in the product in order to improve the AI performance.	
	ARTEMIS	Product platform regarding Utilities. Includes an AI component and is delivered over wireless infrastructure. Impact as described above. The federated learning powered anomaly detection solution designed in WP4 and prototyped in WP5 will be integrated with the ARTEMIS AI algorithms.	Federated Learning powered Anomaly Detection
	AQUAWINGS	Product platform regarding Aquaculture. Includes an AI component and is delivered over wireless infrastructure. Impact as described above. The federated learning powered anomaly detection solutions of DAEMON will improve the performance of AQUAWINGS AI algorithms.	Federated Learning powered Anomaly Detection
	STARLIT	Product platform regarding the Health sector. Includes an AI component and is delivered over wireless infrastructure. Impact as described above. The federated learning powered anomaly detection solutions of DAEMON will improve the performance of STARLIT AI algorithms.	Federated Learning powered Anomaly Detection
ZSCALE	Eclipse Zenoh	Eclipse Zenoh provides a protocol suite for adaptive and distributed data-sharing, to enhance data distribution and flexibility. DAEMON monitoring platform and its interfaces with high-speed data processing can have an impact on the evolutions of this product. Part of DAEMON innovations in decentralized monitoring of infrastructure will be fed into the open-source project Eclipse Zenoh and will be used later to build a complete value chain.	Distributed data-management and decentralized monitoring infrastructure
SRS	srsRAN	srsRAN is a fully open-source 4 and 5G suite including complete UE, RAN, and Core network implementations. During 2023, srsRAN will provide its 5G SA gNB, with O-RAN-compliant architecture and features. Within the DAEMON project, this new architecture will be leveraged to develop and demonstrate the AI-enabled Network Intelligence envisaged by the project. Advancements made during the first two years of the project have helped to inform some of the features that will be rolled out with this new architecture. This will be made available to the project during Y3.	RAN Orchestration

5.2 Patents and Licenses

Based on what we have already achieved so far in terms of technical contributions (as reported in D4.2 [6] and D3.2 [7]), the DAEMON consortium plans two more patent applications during Y3. This is reported above in the partners' individual exploitation plans for Y3.

5.3 Standardization Plan

Based on what we have already achieved so far on the SDO as reported in section 2.3.1, this section provides the plan for the activities and achievements that will be undertaken on standardization for the remaining period of the project.

5.3.1 Standardization Work Plan

Although we have already reached our target number on SDO contributions for the project so far, we will continue our standardization activities in Year 2023 till the end of the project to disseminate the project into the different standardization bodies to enhance awareness and create more opportunities for standardization exploitation.

With the focus on the last project year, it is anticipated that the efforts and activities will be focused on bringing the design of the Network Intelligence Plane and Orchestration, also a few selected DAEMON

innovations and related technology solutions to relevant SDOs, with special effort on preparing proof-of-concept demos.

5.3.2 DAEMON Standardization Roadmap Update

The following figure, Figure 18, shows the planned standardization roadmap for Y3.

	M25-27	M28-30	M31-33	M34-M36
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
O-RAN	O-RAN WG2, WG3, WG6			
ETSI	ETSI-RIS			
	ETSI-ENI			
	ETSI-ZSM			
	ETSI-NFV			
3GPP	Rel 19			
IETF/IRTF	IRTF-NMRG			

Figure 18. Roadmap of SDOs in DAEMON for Y3.

In this roadmap, in addition, to continue our contributions to O-RAN and ETSI RIS, which we already have achieved quite a good number of contributions, we will also enhance the contributions to 3GPP, ETSI ZSM and ENI, and IETF/IRTF. More specifically, TID plans to enhance their work to ENI and ZSM based on their work on network digital twin and anomaly detection and will prepare a PoC on anomaly detection innovation to present for ETSI ENI ISG together with Telefonica Global Solutions. Besides, TID also plans to make additional contributions to IETF/IRTF NMRG, based on the same work on anomaly detection. In terms of O-RAN, NEC and NBL are going to continue actively the contributions to align its further development with the work of DAEMON, with the focus towards the support of more efficient model learning and training, information exposure, energy efficiency, and O-Cloud. In terms of 3GPP/IETF, NBL is following the 3GPP SA2 and IETF ICCRG, particularly on new L4S traffic for use cases such as metaverse or augmented/virtual reality (AR/VR), which will be tied to our application-aware RAN research and other WP3 technological activities related to investigating new algorithms for these new use cases.

It is important to mention that the project partners (NEC, NBL, TID, UC3M, etc.) who have representatives involved in the above-identified SDOs are involved directly in the innovation design and research discussions in DAEMON-related technical work packages, and hence they get steadily informed and updated about the progress and outcome of the project. This ensures that ideas from DAEMON can already flow into these SDOs.

In Y3 we also aim to involve more partners through collaborations to make additional SDO contributions based on the joint work and results. This is our strategy and plan on the standardization activities for the remaining period of the project.

5.4 Open-Source Plan

Contributions to open-source platforms are a key objective of DAEMON, set out to maximize the impact and longevity of the advancements made in the project. By fostering the integration of advancements to NI made by DAEMON into the relevant open-source projects, the project can ensure a significant impact on the open-source community and in leading platforms used in both academia and industry. Any contributions made to the relevant projects should be impactful and significant. They should aim to clearly demonstrate the advancements made to each platform as a result of innovations made by DAEMON.

The project has outlined a goal of 6 contributions to open-source projects over the course of the project as one of the main KPIs for WP6. As mentioned previously, the following open-source platforms have been identified as those most relevant to DAEMON while also having strong links to project partners: srsRAN and Eclipse Zenoh. As of the end of Y2, the project has made five contributions to open-source projects, as outlined in section 2.3.2.

5.4.1 Open-Source Work Plan

The third and final year of the project will focus on demos and PoCs. As a result, technical work will begin to wind down, meaning a potential reduction in possible open-source contributions. This is something the project will need to be cognizant of during Y3. So far, 5 of the 6 planned contributions to open-source

projects have been made. Having already met 80% of the planned open-source contributions, it is important to continue this momentum from Y2 into Y3 where possible.

The main goals for open-source work plan during Y3 are as follows:

- Make at least one more open-source project in line with KPI
- Begin to create a plan to ensure the success of the open-source contributions the project has made, even after the project has ended.

SRS will release their new 5G SA gNB architecture during Y3, which will have features that were directly influenced by the work being done in DAEMON. These features come in the form of O-RAN specific interfaces, such as the E2 interface. Interfaces like this are crucial in B5G networks to develop and demonstrate the AI-enabled Network Intelligence envisaged by the project. This is important not only for the success of the project but to ensure work carried out during the project can be easily adopted within the community and for future research.

In the context of open-source contributions to Eclipse Zenoh during Y3, ZettaScale (in collaboration with the project) have plans to implement new features such as a java binding, a kafka plugin, and DDS plugin instance support. These new extensions will enable DAEMON to integrate zenoh with NI algorithms developed and deployed with different technologies, while keeping a unified data pipeline for the transmission of the data. The Eclipse zenoh roadmap [8] outlines this. With this, the project plans to make at least one contribution to Eclipse Zenoh during Y3.

To ensure the success of DAEMON, beyond the end of the project, we plan to engage with the communities of open-source projects being leveraged. This will be aided by the presence of Zettascale and SRS, the maintainers of these projects, within DAEMON. As a result, we will be aiming to highlight the importance and potential impact DAEMON could have for the open-source community. This engagement will be ongoing throughout the duration of DAEMON, so as to continue to promote the work being done between contributions to open-source projects. This may take the form of tutorial like publications, public demos or involvement in open-source-oriented conferences/ conventions. This is something the project will look into further as Y3 progresses.

The open-source work plan for Y3 is a noticeable change from previous plans made in D6.1 and D6.2, specifically with respect to how we plan to make open-source contributions to srsRAN. This is due to internal issues with permissions for open-sourcing the work of certain partners. This requires a re-structuring of how the project, and SRS, would approach making open-source commitments to srsRAN. Commitments will now be made directly to the main srsRAN repo where possible, as with the DAEMON-inspired features in the 22.10 release, instead of commitments only being made to a project-specific fork of srsRAN hosted on the DAEMON GitHub. This new approach will continue for Y3, as highlighted above. Most notably, with the addition of certain O-RAN features that will be leveraged by the project. This change in approach to open-source contributions by the project and partners shows how DAEMON is committed to ensuring the success of the open-source projects being leveraged and the features DAEMON can add to them.

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